

LIVE RAY TRACING AND AURALIZATION OF 3D AUDIO SCENES WITH VARAYS

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ABSTRACT

We present vaRays, our open-source room acoustic modelling library (C++/Python) that uses acoustic ray tracing to model acoustic interactions of sources, listeners and the virtual environment and auralize the scene in 3D using an ambisonic convolver. The paper describes the different sub-systems of the library: the ray tracer, the ambisonic impulse response encoder and the auralizer, as well as the design choices targeting live auralization of 3D scenes. We demonstrate the use of vaRays with navigation in a 3D model in which sound sources and listener position are communicated to vaRays from a 3D game engine through network message (OSC). We also demonstrate the use of vaRays as a live acoustical simulation system in our large dome, simulating continuously varying acoustic applied to acoustical musical instrument captured with a microphone.

1. INTRODUCTION

At the forefront of live spatial audio research and applications, the *object-based spatialization* [1] paradigm, where sources are located in space using positioning data (azimuth, distance and elevation with reference to the listener), is leading authoring tools and spatial audio compositions. In this paradigm, the spatialization of sound is recreated synthetically by considering the sound sources as points located in space, without the knowledge of the geometry of the simulated space. Inclusion of geometry specific acoustic calculations such as occlusion, sound transfer through materials and reverberation are left to the user.

Fortunately a geometrical scene description (a 3D model), annotated with acoustical properties for each surface, enables the design of algorithm and tools for live computation of spatial audio. More precisely, real-time modelling of the acoustics of a scene at regular intervals is investigated here for virtual reality and immersion applications. Several geometrical acoustic techniques have been described in the past [2] to find acoustic paths between a source-listener pair, such as image-source method, ray tracing and beam tracing. With these paths, a directional specification of the delays and the power of the reverberations constitute what is called the Impulse Response (IR)

of the location for the listener-sound source pair. More precisely, we are interested in real-time auralization, i.e. the process of making audible, by physical or mathematical modelling, the sound field of a sound source in a geometrical space for a specific listener position [3]. This auralization strategy has already been experimented and presented in the literature [2, 4]. It is usually based on live computation of Room Impulse Response (RIR), used to live feed a convolution reverberation.

In this paper, we introduce vaRays, our open-source room acoustic simulation C++ library that aims to address some issues pertaining to acoustic simulation. vaRays uses real-time ray tracing to model the transmission of acoustic energy and its interactions with the environment in a virtual scene. Some of these interactions include absorption by air molecules (air attenuation) and by the surfaces in the virtual environment (material absorption), specular and diffuse reflections, diffraction and transmission through surfaces. Ray tracing is a geometrical acoustic modelling technique [2] where these interactions are modelled by launching rays or packets of energy that travel in straight lines, much like in ray optics to identify the paths through which acoustic energy is transmitted from the sources in a scene to the listener. In vaRays, these modelling results are used to create spatial RIRs in ambisonic format which are then used in the auralization of the virtual scene.

vaRays was first mentioned in [5] as a supplementary tool during its early stages. Here, we discuss vaRays in detail describing the different sub-systems, illustrating and elaborating our design choices. The next section gives an overview of the vaRays pipeline, starting with the scene geometry all the way to auditory output. We provide an overview of vaRays and discuss in detail the different sub-systems of vaRays in Sec. 2, describe in brief a typical usage along with tools built at the Society for arts and technology [SAT] in Sec. 3 and finally conclude and discuss some future pathways in Sec. 4.

2. THE SUB-SYSTEMS OF VARAYS

The vaRays library is primarily written in modern C++ in order to provide acoustic simulation and auralization in real-time on Unix based operating systems. The vaRays software package also includes a Python wrapper for all the important classes for ease of application development and compatibility with popular game engines and 3D animation tools such as Godot and Blender.

vaRays is mainly organized into three mutually exclusive

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sub-systems based on the operations performed, namely:

1. **vaRays Context**, which is responsible for tasks related to the ray tracing operation such as parsing the geometry of the environment, launching and tracing rays and providing simulation results in the form of sound events for each source-listener pair in the scene,
2. **vaRays Encoder**, which is responsible for generating ambisonic RIRs from the ray tracing results,
3. **vaRays Auralizer**, which performs live convolution of audio streams with the RIRs generated by the vaRays encoder.

In the following sections, we describe each of these sub-systems in detail.

2.1 vaRays Context

Acoustic ray tracing is in many ways similar to the ray tracing techniques employed in computer graphics to compute illumination of objects by light sources, with the main difference that sound takes a finite measurable time to travel from a source to a listener, while light can be considered to travel instantaneously for all practical purposes. We use ray tracing to find acoustic paths between the sources and listeners in real time, mainly using methods described in [6]. Since ray tracing is a stochastic technique, the greater the amount of rays thrown, the more accurate the RIRs will be, but the slower the calculations will be as well. New RIRs are generated periodically for every source and listener pair that exists in the scene. The following information is required in order to perform ray tracing:

1. **Sources and listeners:** At least one source and one listener are necessary for the ray tracing to occur. For each pair of source and listener that exists within the scene, one set IRs will be generated (for achieving spatialization - explained in Sec. 2.2). The listeners correspond to coordinates in a scene and do not have a volume. The sources are also coordinates, but vaRays considers them to be spheres with a radius that can be modified by the user.

The main reason for the sources having a volume is to avoid missing rays that are close to the source because of the stochastic nature of ray-tracing. This was first introduced by Vorlander [7]. The larger the volume, the more energy will be picked up by the source. Since volume is only used to calculate energy, it does not interact with the scene. As such, the volume of the source mostly has an incidence on the decay of the energy relative to the distance. A larger volume can, for example, help mitigate unexpected spikes of volume when the listener ventures too close to the source.

Each source also has its own energy level that will be split between each thrown ray. That energy can have a different level depending on frequency, though the default values are evenly distributed. All sources

are considered to be omnidirectional. Directivity for sources is not yet supported, but will be in a future update.

2. **Room geometry:** The geometry is the environment in which rays will be thrown. It is given to the ray tracing engine and updated when required. The geometry contains all surfaces, whose interaction with the incident acoustic rays will be simulated. It however does not contain the sources and listeners as we do not consider collisions with these objects possible during the ray tracing. Geometries are currently loaded using Wavefront OBJ files and do not consider vertex normals (collisions will occur on both faces of a surface regardless).
3. **Materials:** All surfaces in the environment are made of materials which are described by absorption and scattering coefficients in different frequency bands. The scattering coefficients correspond to the proportion of energy that will be diffused during reflections as opposed to reflected specularly. Currently, this coefficient will always be the same regardless of the incident angle of a ray. The absorption coefficient corresponds to the amount of energy that will be lost when a reflection occurs on that surface.

A large amount of stochastic rays are thrown periodically from every listener in a scene. Each of those rays carries an energy map for different frequencies. When a ray hits a surface or a diffraction area, more stochastic rays will be thrown from that point and the energy carried by the initial ray that remains after absorption will be split between children rays. This happens recursively until a maximum reflection order or a minimum energy threshold has been reached for an individual ray. The sources and listeners are not objects in the scene. In order to know if sound reaches its destination, visibility tests are computed from every collision points. Here are the different steps to the ray tracing:

2.1.1 Ray trajectory

It is recommended to throw the rays from listeners, rather than from the sources, which might be unintuitive. The main reason is that when using the diffuse rain method (see Fig. 3) with more than one source in the scene, tracing the rays backwards will greatly reduce the amount of rays to be traced. This will be described with more details in Sec. 2.1.3. While it saves lots of rays from being thrown, this method does have an important drawback. Specular reflections are reciprocal, which means that they will be the same regardless of the point from which we throw the rays. Diffuse reflections are not. While this error is not significant for most room shapes, the possibility of throwing the rays forward always remains if tests show that it is.

2.1.2 Initial rays and direct sound

For each source, the amount of energy emitted from the listener is fixed. Before launching rays, the proportion of energy carried by the direct sound reaching a source with line-of-sight from the listener is calculated as a function of

Figure 1. Direct sound computation for a pair of listener and source.

the solid-angle that it subtends (see Fig. 1). The remaining energy is then distributed equally among the rays that are launched. It is important to note here that no two sources in the scene share the energy launched from the listener, i.e., from the perspective of a given source, all the energy launched from the listener either reach the source or is lost due to absorption, but not received by any other source in the scene.

After the direct sound is computed, the initial rays are thrown. As we throw the ray backwards, rather than containing energy, each ray represents a proportion of receivable energy from the listener. Those rays are sent from a specific point which corresponds to the coordinates of a listener in the scene. The rays are thrown in random directions (uniformly distributed on the surface of a sphere), and the receivable energy is evenly distributed between them. When a ray is thrown, the ray tracer will return the coordinates of the first collision point it reaches (if any) and the material that was defined for that surface.

2.1.3 Reflections

When a thrown ray hits a surface, a reflection event occurs (see Fig. 2). First, the proportion of receivable energy is attenuated by the absorption coefficient of the surface. The remainder is then split in two parts using the scattering coefficient of the surface, the specular and diffuse energies.

Figure 2. Reflection model used in vaRays.

1. **Specular:** A specular reflection will always occur from every reflection point, and it carries the full proportion of receivable specular energy that was calculated previously.
2. **Diffuse:** The amount of diffuse rays sent from every reflection point depends on the user properties (see Fig. 2), and it can change depending on the reflection order. The diffuse proportion of receivable energy at the collision point is evenly split between each diffuse ray that will be created. The proportion of energy that is diffusely reflected from the collision point is evenly split between the Lambertian diffuse rays whose directions are normally distributed about the normal to the surface. This distribution could be changed or modified in the future.

Figure 3. Diffuse rain method.

Before any reflected rays are thrown, a visibility test with each source in the scene is done, similar to what was done to calculate the direct energy. This method is called diffuse rain [6]. If a source is visible, the proportion of specular and diffuse energy that reaches the source is calculated. Since the specular energy only has one specific direction, the proportion that reaches the source is either 0 or 1. In order to calculate the proportion of diffuse energy that reaches the source, we use a variation of the same method we did to calculate the direct energy that reaches the source. The energy that reaches the source is saved (and will contribute to the IR), then subtracted from the sum of energy that will get reflected from that point. Fig. 4 shows the acoustic reflection paths computed by tracing stochastic rays in a virtual environment.

2.2 vaRays Encoder

In this section and Sec. 2.3, we explain our approach to auralization, the process of translating simulation results to auditory output. There are majorly two known methods for auralizing simulation results:

- 1: delay-line based approach, where a single delay-line (or a single output of a multitap delay-line) rep-

(a) In-world viewcaption

(b) Top view

Figure 4. Acoustic paths (orange lines) identified between a source (green ball) and a listener (yellow monkey head) in a model of an 18th century Parisian city block, visualized on Blender.

resents a single acoustic path along with the filter blocks for simulating material absorption,

- 2: convolution based approach, where all acoustic paths are reduced to a finite set of IRs that are convolved with dry/unprocessed audio signal from the source.

The first approach is very effective in auralizing dynamic scenes (moving listeners and sources) by updating delay lengths and filter coefficients at audio-rate [4], thus being able to auralize acoustic phenomena such as Doppler shift. However, it suffers from the major disadvantage of being computationally expensive for dense simulations with large number of acoustic paths.

The second approach is very efficient in auralizing dense simulations (computational cost is fixed for fixed IR lengths) but is not effective in auralizing dynamic scenes and requires filter update mechanisms. In vaRays, we take a hybrid approach exploiting both techniques. The computation of IRs for convolution is discussed in detail in

this section and the auralization system is explained in Sec. 2.3.1.

Assuming all interactions between the acoustic rays and the acoustic surfaces in the scene are linear and time-invariant (LTI), static source-room-listener systems can be considered as LTI systems described by RIRs. For any given scene configuration, the vaRays context provides us with the following information about acoustic paths between each source-listener pair, using which the vaRays encoder computes spatialized RIRs in higher-order-ambisonic (HOA) format:

1. **Path distance:** The distance travelled by the ray from the listener to the sources after reflections.
2. **Direction of departure:** The initial direction in which the ray was launched from the listener. This information is essential for spatialization of the RIR.
3. **Energy profile:** The energy distribution of the ray over pre-determined frequency bands (explained in greater detail later in this section).

An RIR is essentially a series of delayed, filtered and scaled Dirac impulses corresponding to the acoustic paths between a source and a listener (currently in vaRays, the phase evolution of the impulses during propagation is not considered). The vaRays encoder essentially builds convolution kernels (signals with which the dry audio signal from the source is convolved) from the time-energy-space echograms produced by the ray tracer. We employ filter updating techniques to auralize dynamic scenes from static RIRs (explained in Sec. 2.3). In real-time auralization of dynamic scenes, computing these spatial RIRs with minimal time delay is critical in maximizing immersion [8]. We mainly considered two approaches to generating RIRs, but we only discuss the approach that better suits real-time auralization requirements in this paper. Detailed account of the experiments and choice of approach can be found here¹.

Each ray reaching a source from the listener is filtered by the surfaces participating in its propagation due to their acoustic properties (frequency dependent absorption, transmission and scattering) and attenuated due to air absorption. The vaRays material property database (mostly derived from [8] and [4]) contains properties defined for 8 octave bands between the range of 125 - 16000 Hz. Air absorption coefficients are computed [9] for these frequency bands on start-up and are saved for use during auralization. In vaRays, we take a source-filter approach to generate RIRs by supplying excitation pulses as input to a perfect-reconstruction filter-bank.

We make use of a digital Linkwitz-Riley [10] crossover filter tree that consists of filter pairs as shown in Fig. 5. The Linkwitz-Riley filter pair is made of a 4th-order Butterworth highpass and lowpass filter with their critical frequencies at the crossover point (the frequency separating two adjacent bands). This filter structure is known for its orthogonality property and is widely used in loudspeaker

¹ https://gitlab.com/sat-metalab/vaRays/-/tree/master/Playground/IR_Generation, accessed May 2021.

crossover circuits and digital multi-band processing. In our context, we use the LR filter tree as the filter in the source-filter model with 8 inputs corresponding to the 8 octave bands.

Figure 5. Block diagram of the Linkwitz-Riley crossover filter tree used for generating RIRs in vaRays. Blocks with flat line followed by decreasing ramp are lowpass filters and those with increasing ramp followed by flat line are highpass filters. The inputs to the filter tree are excitation impulse trains (left extreme) corresponding to bands between the crossover frequencies indicated by dotted lines, and the output is the RIR (right extreme).

An LR filter tree with N stages (here $N = 3$) has 2^N inputs for a different frequency band (8 inputs). Each stage I of the filter tree is responsible for band-merging at crossover frequencies f_i where $i = I + n * (2^{I+1})$ and $n \in 0, 1, \dots, 2^{N-(I+1)} - 1$. The all-pass filters (denoted by the letter A in Fig. 5) compensate for the phase shifts caused by the LR filter pairs on the other branches of the tree.

For a mono IR, the vaRays encoder first generates a train of Dirac impulses delayed by an amount proportional to the propagation path of the rays and scaled proportional to the energy contained in each frequency band, giving a total of 8 excitation impulse trains to be fed synchronously to the corresponding inputs of the LR filter tree. The output of the filter-tree is a mono IR. For an ambisonic RIR of order N_{ambi} , the same structure is repeated for each of the $(N_{ambi} + 1)^2$ ambisonic channels with the impulses being scaled additionally by the ambisonic coefficients for the direction of departure of the ray from the listener. vaRays currently supports only up to 6th order SN3D ambisonic format.

This approach to generating RIRs scales very well with increasing density of simulation with increasing number of acoustic paths for a source-listener pair. Table 1 shows the time taken to generate IRs of different lengths and different number of acoustic paths on a laptop with i5-4200M processor and 8 GB of RAM. It can be seen that the time taken remains relatively unchanged across different number of acoustic paths and the depends only on the lengths of the generated IRs.

IR Length (samples)	Computation Time / IR (ms)			
	Number of Acoustic Paths			
	10k	25k	50k	100k
24000	6.0	5.8	6.2	6.1
48000	11.3	11.3	11.4	12.0
96000	23.6	23.4	23.7	24.8

Table 1. Computation time of IRs of different lengths and different number acoustic paths.

2.3 vaRays Auralizer

”Auralization” is the process of sonification of the acoustics in an environment by means of physical and mathematical modelling of the propagation of acoustic energy to induce a sense of immersion in the space [3]. In vaRays, the auralizer subsystem is responsible for producing audio output for a given scene configuration.

The vaRays auralizer uses the *zita-convolver* library by Fons Adriaensen² to convolve audio signals from sources with their respective RIRs using the non-uniform partitioned overlap-and-save method (NUPOLS) [11]. The NUPOLS method is a block convolution algorithm where the IR is partitioned into chunks of non-decreasing lengths to provide zero latency and increased computational efficiency.

In dynamically changing scene configurations, the RIRs also change dynamically, requiring live updates to the convolution kernel. Several additions were made to the *zita-convolver* in order to facilitate real-time IR updates. Smooth transition between IRs during updates is necessary to avoid audible artifacts especially in highly dynamic scenes considering the stochastic nature of the ray tracing algorithm and the absence of path tracking mechanism. Cross-fading between the old and the new IR is a popular method for smooth transition and there are several ways in which this can be accomplished. Some IR update strategies are described in chapter 6 of [12].

Among the ones described, the two main strategies we considered were: 1) the immediate coherent exchange, where all the IR partitions are simultaneously cross-faded over one partition duration, and 2) the successive asynchronous exchange, where the IR partitions are cross-faded successively. After experimentation, we chose the first method since for very long IRs the updates are instantaneous, hence reducing the wait time for all partitions to be swapped. However, the drawback of this method is that if the new IR is much longer than the previous one, the older buffered samples will erroneously be convolved with the new IR and become audible. This can be overcome by a hybrid approach where the immediate coherent exchange strategy is employed when the IR length decreases and successive asynchronous exchange strategy is used when it increases. This will be implemented in vaRays in a future release.

Another important acoustic phenomenon that takes place in dynamic environments with moving sources and listen-

²<http://kokkinizita.linuxaudio.org/linuxaudio/index.html>, accessed March 2021.

ers is Doppler shift [13]. In vaRays, this is auralized by the Doppler shift engine.

2.3.1 Doppler shift engine

The change in apparent frequency of sound due to relative motion between the source and the listener is known as Doppler shift or Doppler effect. In room acoustic simulators that use the delay-line approach for auralization [4], Doppler shift can be produced by updating delay lengths at audio-rate. However, it is impossible to produce Doppler shift in auralization systems that use the convolution approach. In vaRays, we use a delay-line based Doppler shift engine like in [14], alongside the convolution engine to auralize Doppler shift only for direct paths and ignore the reflected paths. With the addition of a path tracking mechanism, Doppler shift may be produced for persistent reflected paths as well.

Doppler effect depends on the instantaneous relative velocity between a source and a listener, which is usually provided by game physics engines. However, in the absence of a game physics engine, the instantaneous velocities must be computed from positional information. In vaRays, we use a high resolution clock to measure the time difference between successive positional updates for each source-listener pair to estimate the relative velocity.

3. EXAMPLE USAGE

In this section, we discuss two different use cases for vaRays which we have tested:

- Live navigation in a 3D model filled with sound sources, spatialized with vaRays and rendered into binaural audio³.
- Live auralization of live acoustical instrument while navigating in geometry displayed inside our 12-meter large dome⁴.

Before describing these use cases in more detail, we introduce the technical pipeline in which vaRays has been integrated with the other tools built at the SAT.

3.1 Technical pipeline

There are three main components in the pipeline:

1. Edition-In-Situ [15] (EiS), a 3D environment for in-situ editing of a virtual scene. We use this tool for visualization and navigation of the environment in real-time.
2. a vaRays application developed in C++ using the vaRays library. This application provides the interface required to modify the virtual environment and perform acoustic simulation in real-time.

³ The following video, <https://vimeo.com/507255065>, accessed March 2021 shows an example of the Bretez use case.

⁴ The following video, <https://vimeo.com/484122810>, accessed March 2021, shows a live auralization of acoustical instruments using vaRays.

3. SATIE [16], a spatial audio scene manager for decoding the ambisonic audio stream in binaural. SATIE is also capable of decoding the ambisonic stream into VBAP for auralization in multi-speaker setups [5].

Fig. 6 shows a block diagram indicating communication between the three components in the pipeline. This pipeline requires an active Jack audio⁵ server for routing audio between vaRays and SATIE. The ambisonic order to be used for auralization is set on start-up and a corresponding number of Jack output ports for vaRays and Jack input ports for SATIE are created. Further, a number of JACK output ports are created for SATIE to stream the decoded audio stream. For example, 2 output ports are created when decoding the ambisonic output of vaRays to binaural.

Figure 6. Information flow between different pipeline components.

The acoustic scene in vaRays is updated via OSC messages from EiS. Each time a new source is created, EiS creates a Jack output port with the selected audio source stream and sends an OSC message to vaRays to create a new Jack input port to receive the stream to be convolved with the generated RIR for the source. When a source or the listener moves in the scene, the new positions are updated via OSC and a new ray tracing iteration is triggered in vaRays to recompute the ambisonic IR. The output ambisonic stream from vaRays contains the entire scene audio, i.e., it is a sum of ambisonic streams from all sources in the scene, for a fixed listener orientation. The ambisonic rotation corresponding to the listener orientation is performed by SATIE before the binaural decoding based on Euler angles received directly from EiS.

3.2 Bretez

The Bretez project aims at developing immersive editing tools for historians, helping in creating immersive experiences of 18th century Paris [17]. In order to simulate realistic audio in real time, we use the vaRays with the pipeline described in Sec. 3.1. The ray tracing computation time depends on the complexity of the room geometry in the scene. It is advised to use a low-resolution/low-poly version of the room geometry to speed up the ray tracing process while maintaining acoustic simulation quality, thereby reducing the latency between scene changes and the auralized output. We, however, use a high resolution model

⁵ <https://github.com/jackaudio/jackaudio>. github.com/wiki, accessed March 2021.

for graphic rendering on EiS for a better visual experience. Fig. 7 shows the models used for graphics and acoustics in this demonstration.

(a) Model used for graphic rendering

(b) Low resolution/low-poly model used for acoustic ray tracing

Figure 7. Two version of the 18th century Paris from the Bretez project. These two versions are aligned and optimized for the two following separate operations: graphic rendering and audio ray tracing.

3.3 Live auralization

We have also used the pipeline described in Sec. 3.1 to create a live auralization experience using vaRays, except for SATIE providing ambisonic order three decoded for our dome speaker system. By using only one source within the scene and using the same coordinates as the listener for it, we create an acoustic experience that corresponds to experiencing the acoustics of a simulated room geometry. We use a mono microphone input as the one source, simulating in real time your own presence in a virtual room. We have tested this by moving the editor in the virtual environment in real time while recording acoustic instruments with the microphone and playing it back in a multichannel audio setup using ambisonic decoding.

4. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

In this paper, we have described vaRays and its different sub-systems in detail along with some design approaches, challenges and known shortcomings of the library. This library is intended for use with popular game engines and 3D renderers supporting C++ or Python scripting, making an attempt to reduce the threshold of entry into the world of acoustic simulation and facilitate more realistic artistic and immersive experiences.

The choice of Python for a first wrapper around the C++ library is to further simplify integration of vaRays into different software tools, since Python has lately become the de-facto programming language for integrating software building blocks.

Future work will be on the inclusion of transmission of energy through surfaces, diffraction and source directivity in the physical simulation of acoustic propagation, all of which should increase its realism. Alternative simulation methods should be considered for late reverberations as this implies a lot of reflections (hence computations) with our ray-tracing approach.

We are also working in the direction of simulating non-fixed 3D scenes which is mostly a matter of updating the 3D geometry used for ray-tracing, as well as on the creation of multiple datasets comprised of physical measurements of room impulse responses and 3D reconstruction of the recorded location, to allow for validating the employed simulation method.

Lastly, even though the current implementation can handle realtime simulation there is room for many optimizations which should be applied before our method is compared to other methods, like geometrical acoustic solvers for example.

We, at SAT, strongly believe in open-source software since it bolsters scientific and technological evolution by democratizing knowledge. By making vaRays open-source, like the other tools developed at SAT, we hope it will greatly benefit the community of digital artists and acoustic researchers alike.

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